

Whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) and leafroller (LF) in Haryana

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WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* Horvath caused widespread hopperburn, and a severe outbreak of LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée occurred in Haryana in 1983 kharif. WBPH population reached 5-10 insects/hill in mid-Sep and epidemic levels in mid-Oct when sweep net samples from highly infested fields had 1,000-1,500 insects/sweep (see table). Seventy percent of the fields had hopperburn. PR106 and local Basmata were seriously damaged.

LF populations peaked in Oct, when about two-thirds of the leaves in infested

WBPH and LF damage in Haryana, India, 1983 kharif.

District	Block	Villages surveyed (no.)	WBPH infestation	LF (% leaf infestation)
Kurukshetra	Thaneshwar	9	Very severe	70
	Pehowa	11	Very severe	75
	Pundri	8	Very severe	50
	Radaur	5	Severe	23
Karnal	Nilokheri	8	Severe	25
	Indri	6	Moderate	22
Ambala	Ambala	6	Moderate	15
	Jagadhari	7	Moderate	22

fields were folded (see table). Most damaged plants were white with papery leaves.

Factors that may have contributed to the insect outbreaks include

- early, heavy monsoon rains followed by a long period of dry, humid weather;

- application of 175-250 kg N/ha; and
 - poor WBPH control by recommended insecticides.
- Selective insecticides for WBPH control are needed and the extent of yield reduction caused by LF should be determined. *J*

Relation between brown planthopper (BPH) biotype 2 infestation and sheath blight (ShB) infection

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IR22, IR36, ASD7, and Utri Rajapan

were tested to learn if BPH infestation increased ShB infection. Treatments were male BPH + ShB, female BPH + ShB, and ShB alone (Table 1). BPH infestation did not affect ShB severity. Results also showed that IR22 and IR36 were more resistant to ShB than Utri Rajapan and ASD7 (Table 2). *J*

Sex ratio and productive status of *Scotinophara coarctata* collected from light traps and rice fields

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Adult black bugs *Scotinophara coarctata* (F.) were collected from light traps, street lights, and rice fields in Malaysia and the Philippines to determine their sex ratio and reproductive status.

In Sep-Nov 1984, 755 adults were collected from rice fields and 792 on fluorescent street lights or in light traps at several sites on Palawan, Philippines. In Malaysia, 173 black bugs were collected from fields and 478 from street lights. All samples were sexed and preserved in 85% ethyl alcohol. Each female was dissected to determine her reproductive status: no eggs present, eggs beginning to form in ovarioles, oviducts approximately half full of eggs, and gravid.

Philippine fields yielded 44% males and 56% females; light traps and street lights, 49% males and 51% females. The trend was similar in Malaysia, where field collections were 64% females. But

Table 1. Mean lesion length of BPH-infested and ShB-infected rice plants, IRRI.

Treatment	Lesion length ^a (mm)				
	Utri Rajapan	ASD7	IR36	IR22	Mean
Male BPH + ShB	287 a	321 ab	112 c	107 c	207 a
Female BPH + ShB	395 b	352 ab	146 c	130 c	256 a
ShB	339 ab	309 ab	125 c	108 c	220 a
Mean	340 a	328 a	128 b	115 b	228

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

Table 2. Mean number and length of ShB lesions on different rices, IRRI.

Days after inoculation	Variety		Difference ^a
	Utri Rajapan and ASD7	IR36 and IR22	
	<i>Lesions (no.)</i>		
7	4.2	3.4	0.8 ns
14	7.0	4.3	2.7**
21	8.8	4.0	4.8**
28	9.6	5.2	4.4**
	<i>Lesion length (mm)</i>		
7	118	66	52**
14	200	89	111**
21	367	122	245**
28	652	210	442**

^a ns = not significant at 5% level, ** = significant at 1% level.